

Current trends in children's risky behaviour in the online environment through the case study of E-Safety counselling

Kopecký, Kamil, Voráč, Dominik, Szotkowski, René, Dobešová, Pavla, Krejčí, Veronika
Faculty of Education, Palacký University in Olomouc

Annotation

The article focuses on the analysis of current forms of risky communication of children and adolescents in the digital environment. The authors from the Centre for the Prevention of Risky Virtual Communication at the Faculty of Education of the University of Olomouc processed a set of 901 case studies dealt with by the *E-Bezpečí* Internet Counselling Centre in the years 2013-2025.

Qualitative content analysis included classification of cases by phenomenon (e.g., sextortion, sexting, cyberbullying, phishing, grooming), roles of participants, gender of the victim, platform used, and time frame. The results show an increasing trend in the prevalence of some forms of risk behaviour – in particular sextortion, sexting and cyberbullying - with the key period in terms of the increase in these phenomena being adolescence (13-16 years). Girls made up a significant majority of the clinic's clientele, and statistical analysis revealed significant gender differences in the reporting of sexting and online hate.

1. Introduction

Children's risky behaviour in the online environment

Children today come into contact **with digital technologies at an early age**. A cross-sectional study found that almost all children aged 6 months to 4 years (96.6%) use mobile devices, with the majority starting before the age of one. By age two, many children are already using a mobile device daily, with screen time comparable to television viewing time, and by age four, a significant proportion of children already own a device (Kabali et al, 2015). This trend becomes even more pronounced as age increases, with 95% of US adolescents reporting owning or having access to a smartphone, according to a Pew Research Center report (Anderson & Jiang, 2018). Similar patterns can be observed in Europe, with an updated meta-analysis showing that in the UK, more than half of children (53%) acquire their first smartphone around the age of seven (Mori et al., 2022). And comparable trends have been observed in the Czech Republic (Dobesova et al., 2023).

Digital technologies play a significant role in the lives of children and adults. They facilitate access to information, foster creativity and provide a space for identity formation and the development of social connections (Moreno & Radesky, 2023). However, **in addition to these benefits, they also present a number of challenges** that can threaten the safety of users, especially children. These risks include not only unsafe

interactions with other users, but also exposure to harmful content that they may encounter in the online environment. Information and communication technologies have also enabled the development of new forms of interpersonal communication, including the sharing of visual and textual content. One of these forms is the creation and transmission of sexually explicit material via the Internet and smartphones, which poses specific risks associated with its unauthorized dissemination and misuse (Gámez-Guadix et al., 2021). This issue is part of Technology-Facilitated Sexual Violence (TFSV), which includes various forms of sexual aggression in the online environment, such as **online grooming, sextortion, revenge porn**, etc. (Amadori & Brighi, 2025).

The most typical forms of risky behaviour in the online environment include **aggressive acts** such as swearing, insults, labelling, threats or blackmail. These acts may also include the dissemination of photographs or videos with the aim of humiliating the victim. The use of digital technologies has made it possible for peer violence to take place online anytime and anywhere, making so-called **cyberbullying** a significant risk associated with online violence among children and adolescents (Pérez-Rodríguez et al, 2024). With the increasing availability of Internet communication and social media, the prevalence of cyberbullying and psychosocial problems among adolescents has increased in recent years (Öztürk et al., 2025; Santre, 2023).

Cyberbullying is deliberate, repeated and hostile behaviour that is carried out through electronic communication tools with the intention of harming another individual. It is characterized by the intensity of the attacks, their repetition, and their public nature, which can have long-term and lasting consequences for the victim, especially in cases where sensitive content is disseminated and removal is not always possible (Hasse et al., 2019; Kumar & Goldstein, 2020; Leduc et al., 2022).

The "2021 Cyberbullying Data" study (Hinduja & Patchin, 2021) analyzed data collected in April 2019 from a representative sample of 4,972 elementary and middle school sophomores ages 12 to 17 in the United States. Results showed that 17.4% of respondents reported experiencing cyberbullying as a victim, while 4.9% admitted to having perpetrated it themselves. A 2024 follow-up survey by the Cyberbullying Research Center (Hinduja & Patchin, 2024) compiled data from 5,005 U.S. students aged 13 to 17 years, collected in May and June 2023. According to these results, 26.5% of respondents reported being a victim of cyberbullying within the past 30 days, reflecting the current prevalence rate of the phenomenon among the adolescent population.

At the same time, research confirms that the prevalence of cyberbullying among adolescents is not consistent - according to a systematic review, the prevalence of cyberbullying from the perspective of victims ranges from 13.99% to 57.5%, while the prevalence of perpetrators ranges from 6.0% to 46.3%. These differences are influenced by a number of individual factors, such as age, gender, or previous experiences of victimization, as well as contextual factors, such as the quality of family relationships, school climate, or geographic setting (Zhu et al., 2021). The chosen methodology of the research study also has an important influence – in a broader definition, almost any aggressive behaviour in an online environment can be considered cyberbullying, while a narrower definition sees it as behaviour that meets specific criteria, such as repetition, intensity or severe impact on the victim (Hollá, 2013; Kopecký, 2016; Kopecký & Szotkowski, 2017).

Data are also available on the lifetime prevalence of cyberbullying, i.e. the occurrence of this phenomenon at any time in the respondent's life. In the United States, for example, repeated surveys show that the proportion of adolescents who have experienced cyberbullying at some point in their lives is increasing - while in 2007, around 18% of high school students reported this experience, in 2019 it is already around 36% (Hinduja & Patchin, 2019 in López-Vizcaíno et al., 2021). This increase can be partly explained by the growing use of digital technologies, mobile devices and social networks among children and youth (López-Vizcaíno et al., 2021).

However, the use of lifetime prevalence in the context of adolescent development is subject to criticism. These data are based on heterogeneous studies using different methodological approaches, which complicates their comparison with each other. As Kopecký (2016) points out, lifetime data may distort the actual prevalence of cyberbullying, as the time period is not uniform among respondents - for some it may be an experience that is several months old, while for others it may be a childhood event. From a methodological perspective, it is therefore preferable to focus on the occurrence of cyberbullying within a well-defined time frame, ideally over the last few weeks or months, which allows for more accurate intergenerational and international comparisons.

One specific form of cyberbullying is **body shaming**, in which the victim is confronted with negative comments about their appearance. These comments may not always be intentionally harmful, but can have serious consequences (Kraag et al., 2021). This phenomenon is often confused with *appearance teasing* (repeated comments ridiculing appearance), *trolling* (deliberate, often anonymous teasing) and *cyberbullying* (repeated hurtful behaviour online, often involving power imbalance), and *body shaming* differs from these in that it does not have to be repeated and does not have to involve power imbalance (Kraag et al., 2021). It is particularly problematic in online settings due to the persistent availability of visual content (Leduc et al., 2022). Studies show that a quarter of teenagers have experienced body shaming from family or peers (Cerolini et al., 2024), although this type of verbal-emotional violence is often considered acceptable (Schlüter et al., 2023). If body shaming is repeated, it can become part of cyberbullying (Kraag et al., 2021). There is still a lack of a consistent definition of body shaming and its relationship to other forms of social aggression (Kraag et al., 2021; Schlüter et al., 2023).

In recent years, **there has been a significant increase in cases of attacks on children that involve sexual content** such as intimate photographs or videos (Patchin & Hinduja, 2022). These attacks can be divided into situations where the victim does not know the aggressor, such as an unknown "peer" online who is actually a perpetrator with different intentions. And situations where the victim knows the aggressor, e.g., an ex-partner, a classmate (Sztokowski et al., 2020). Different terms are then used for attacks using sexual content: *sextortion*, *revenge porn*, *online blackmailing*, etc. All of these forms are part of a broader phenomenon known as Non-Consensual Image-Based Sexual Abuse (NCII), which refers to the unauthorized dissemination of intimate material (Brighi et al., 2023).

Sextortion refers to the blackmailing of a victim by threatening to disclose intimate materials in order to coerce them into a specific action, such as providing additional materials, sexual acts, or a sum of money (Ray & Henry, 2024). This phenomenon, referred to as the new sex crime of the digital age (Wittes et al., 2016), occurs in a variety of

contexts such as intimate partner abuse, cyberbullying, and human trafficking (Cross, Holt, & Holt, 2023; Henry & Umbach, 2024). Perpetrators can be intimate partners, strangers online, or members of criminal groups (Patchin & Hinduja, 2024). The prevalence among youth ranges between 0.7% and 5%, and is as high as 18.7% among adults (Henry & Umbach, 2024).

Revenge porn refers to the publication of intimate material without the victim's consent, usually with the aim of getting revenge on a former partner after a break-up. It is a specific form of abuse of intimate materials in interpersonal relationships that aims to harm or hurt the victim, to take revenge (Brighi et al., 2023; Walker & Sleath, 2017). This phenomenon has serious psychological, social, and legal consequences, with victims often facing not only public shame but also secondary victimization (Gámez-Guadix et al., 2022; Henry et al., 2019). Research among young Italian adults showed that 3.3% of respondents had been victims of unauthorized dissemination of intimate material (Brighi et al., 2023).

Online blackmailing includes sextortion and other forms of digital blackmail. Perpetrators use phishing, deepfake technology, and social engineering to manipulate victims (Cross, Holt, & O'Malley, 2023). Victims often do not report incidents due to shame and fear, with only approximately 40% of incidents being reported to parents or other authorities (Patchin & Hinduja, 2024). Online extortion through internet services and social networking sites poses a serious threat to children and adolescents. Research conducted by the Centre for Prevention of Risky Virtual Communication at the Faculty of Education of Palacký University in Olomouc found that 6-8% of Czech children have been victims of this phenomenon, with perpetrators using repeated manipulative techniques such as building trust, obtaining intimate content and then blackmailing (Kopecký, 2017). Alarmingly, none of the child victims sought adult help during the first two to three months of the extortion, which increases the risk of long-term psychological consequences. Psychological consequences include depression, anxiety, or suicidal ideation (Gámez-Guadix et al., 2022; Walsh & Tener, 2022). These data underscore the need for preventive measures and early intervention.

These unsafe behaviours are related to **sexting**, a form of intimate communication involving the sharing of erotic or sexual content online that is increasingly common in today's digital society (Ojeda et al., 2024). Its prevalence has been increasing in recent years, with an increasing trend observed with age and advancing technological capabilities. Studies show that sexting is more common among adolescents aged 16 to 18 years than among younger groups aged 14 to 15 years (Quesada et al., 2018). In a Spanish study, the prevalence of sexting among adolescents aged 12 to 18 years was found to be 24%, with 61% of respondents reporting that they had engaged in sexting at least once (Molla-Esparza et al., 2021). In a meta-analysis of 39 studies, the average prevalence of sending sexts was 14.8%, with 27.4% of young people reporting receiving sexts (Madigan et al., 2018a). According to research in the Czech Republic, sexting in the form of sending text messages of an intimate nature is practiced by 25.92% of Czech children, with intimate photographs sent by 15.68% and intimate videos by 5.9%. Sexting materials in the form of photographs were received by 40.65% of children, videos by 21.04%, and more than one-fifth of children have witnessed another person getting naked via video chat (Szotkowski et al., 2020). The beginnings of sexting in the Czech Republic have already been recorded in children aged 7 to 10 years, which shows that this

phenomenon appears at an early age. 7% of respondents in this age group sent a "sexy" text message, 5% shared a provocative photo and 5% a video of a similar nature. Approximately 14% of respondents said they received an erotic message, and 11% received an intimate photo or video. Platforms such as Skype, Instagram, Facebook and WhatsApp were most commonly used for sexting. The study also showed that 18% of children visited a video chat room, with 6% encountering sexual content and 3% exposing themselves (Dobesova et al., 2023). It should be added that sexting is often in response to a sext sent, thus happening in return (Renfrow & Rollo, 2014). Motivations for sexting tend to be expressions of mutual desire and trust in romantic relationships (Döring, 2014; Gala & Kapadia, 2013), responses to boredom (Anastassiou, 2017), or social pressure (Lippman & Campbell, 2014; Ringrose et al., 2012). Thus, the realization of sexting is often associated with partner relationships where persons know each other in the real world, but it can also occur in casual communication when establishing relationships with strangers, such as in social networking sites (Almeida & Pereira, 2025). In these interactions, there are serious risks when adults use fake profiles and manipulate children to induce them to send intimate material, which they then misuse. This form of communication can become a tool for manipulation, leading to dangerous consequences, including blackmail (Mori et al., 2020; Wachs et al., 2021).

Other types of risky behaviour include various **scams** that occur **in the online environment**. One of the most vulnerable groups is seniors (Chen et al., 2025). Due to the increasing use of digital technologies and lack of awareness, they face the risk of serious financial and emotional losses. Fraudsters often exploit their gullibility and lack of experience with cyberspace. Some of the most common practices include fake medical products, investment scams, false offers of retirement savings, or fake romantic relationships (D. Wang et al., 2025). These relationships often involve upfront fee scams, where perpetrators promise future benefits or affection in exchange for payments that are never fulfilled (Abubakari, 2024). However, it is not only seniors who are at risk. Scams are also increasingly spreading through instant messengers and social networks, where scams related to m-payments, phishing or fake investment offers, for example, are emerging. Victims of these scams go through different emotional phases, ranging from hope and anticipation at the beginning to anxiety, disappointment and disgust (J. Wang et al., 2024), especially when it comes to online shopping and bazaar scams, where buyers and sellers are manipulated or offered non-existent products. Losses can be substantial, not least because of the difficulty in recovering refunds (Zeng et al., 2025). Fraudulent practices also occur in the online gaming environment, where theft of game accounts, unauthorised trading of virtual items or misuse of payment details in in-game ecosystems are common. Here, fraudsters target gamers of all ages, taking advantage of their inattention or lack of account protection. (Kristiansen et al., 2024) As these scams can trigger feelings of shame, guilt or helplessness in victims, many people are hesitant to report them and seek help. In such cases, **anonymous online counselling sites** can play a key role, providing a safe space to share experiences and seek solutions without the need for personal identification.

Why children use anonymous counselling

The use of anonymous counselling by children and adolescents can be placed in the broader context of online help-seeking in mental health. A study (Pretorius et al.,

2019) shows that young people aged 18-25 often use the internet to seek support for personal and emotional problems, with anonymity and privacy playing a key role in their decision-making. These factors are equally crucial for children and adolescents who turn to anonymous online counselling services. Although the topic of online counselling is relevant to them, few studies have looked in detail at the motivations behind children's decisions to use anonymous online counselling.

According to statistics from the Centre for the Prevention of Risky Virtual Communication (Centrum *PRVoK*, 2025), which has been operating an anonymous counselling centre for victims of risky behaviour on the Internet since 2010, it appears that children aged 13 to 16 most often report their problems. Younger children turn to counselling less frequently, and for children under 10 it is mostly informed parents who report the incident. Child clients prefer to talk anonymously because they fear that their problem might leak out to their neighbourhood (e.g. a teacher would inform their parents about the problem). However, the fear of the parents' reaction if the children confide the problem to them is quite dominant. They fear that parents would react inappropriately, for example, by addressing the situation by banning technologies they normally use. They want to avoid this and resolve the situation without the parents' knowledge.

Similar motivations have been found among older adolescents and young adults in international research. (Pretorius et al., 2019) found in their study that 80% of respondents would use a mobile phone to seek help for personal or emotional problems and 82.57% would use an internet search engine to do so. For this reason, anonymous feedback is an absolutely crucial tool for children, allowing them to openly share their concerns and seek support without putting themselves at risk of unwanted interference from adults. However, anonymity also brings with it certain challenges - for example, the risk that serious cases will not be adequately addressed. It is therefore essential to strike a balance between the protection of privacy and the need for early intervention, especially in situations that threaten a child's safety and health. In serious cases, parental involvement in the solution is absolutely necessary (e.g. reporting the problem to the police).

2. Methods

This study focused on analysing current trends in children's risky behaviour in online environments by examining case reports provided by the E-Bezpečí helpline of Centre for prevention of risky virtual communication at Faculty of Education, Palacký University in Olomouc, accessible via the website www.napisnam.cz. The helpline, which has been addressing cases of online risk behaviour since 2010, has handled more than 5,000 cases to date. As such, it represents an established and regularly utilized service within the Czech internet landscape, frequently accessed by both children and adults.

For the purposes of this study, we analyzed case reports spanning the period from June 6, 2013, to February 13, 2025, from children that were 10 to 17 years old. In accordance with the platform's terms of use, respondents were informed that anonymized cases might be used for research purposes. Our analysis included all available cases, excluding only those unrelated to internet-related phenomena.

All analysed cases were anonymized in accordance with ethical principles governing the protection of personal data and the privacy of respondents. Identifiable information, including first and last names, school names, street names, and any other details that could lead to individual identification, was removed.

The study received ethical approval from the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Education at Palacký University Olomouc.

For the purposes of this study, case records from counseling practice related to various forms of risky behavior in digital environments were analyzed. The data consisted of qualitative material obtained in the form of anonymized messages (inquiries) addressed to the helpline. Given the nature of these communications, the primary objective was to identify recurring patterns and to structure the data in a manner that would allow for both descriptive and, subsequently, interpretative analysis.

The categorization of cases was conducted in multiple stages:

1. **Thematic Classification (Phenomenon)** - Each case was initially classified according to the primary phenomenon addressed in the inquiry-such as sextortion, cyberbullying, unlawful dissemination of intimate materials, manipulation on social networks, and similar issues.
2. **Participant Roles** - Subsequently, the role of the author and the person directly affected by the issue was identified (in most cases, the author of the submission was also the affected individual).
3. **Victim's Gender** - In the majority of cases, the gender of the victim was also determined, as the Czech grammatical system uses gender-specific verb endings in the past tense. However, in several instances, gender could not be identified, or the case involved multiple victims of different genders.
4. **Platform and Medium of Occurrence** - The next step involved identifying the platform on which the described event occurred (e.g., Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, online games, etc.).

5. **Temporal Identification** - Each case was assigned a date (or a time period) based on when the message was received, allowing for the tracking of potential temporal trends.
6. **Content Coding** - The qualitative messages were further enriched by a set of thematic codes representing meaning-bearing units (e.g., deteriorated mental health, self-harm, sharing content with others, etc.).

Even without further work on the coded data, it was possible to quantify several fundamental characteristics of the cases—such as the frequency of individual phenomena, gender distribution, platform representation, and the roles of message authors. This approach enables the combination of qualitative depth with clear descriptive statistics, thereby contributing to a better understanding of the dynamics of online risks.

To enhance the validity of the analysis, a peer-review method was implemented. One member of the research team analyzed one portion of the case reports, while a second member analyzed another. They then reviewed each other's outputs. The entire dataset was subsequently reviewed by the lead author of the study, who conducted the final revision.

This process ensured transparency and scientific credibility in the analytical procedure. The combination of collaborative coding and subsequent reflection allowed for a balanced interpretation of the case meanings while maintaining systematic rigor. Nonetheless, some degree of distortion may still occur, as certain cases were ambiguous or straddled multiple subcategories (e.g., instances of cyberbullying that also involved manipulation of photographs). In such cases, classification was based on the dominant feature of the case.

Based on the content analysis of individual messages, an analytical typology of digital risks was developed and applied. The categorization was grounded in relevant theoretical frameworks from cyberpsychology and existing research on digital threats affecting children and adolescents. This typology was continuously validated through team discussions. Each case was assigned to a primary category according to the dominant phenomenon described in the report. The categorization considered both the motivation of the perpetrator and the impact on the victim. The categories are illustrated in figure 1.

Figure 1

Categories of virtual risky behavior cases with descriptions and examples

Category	Description	Example
Sextortion	This category includes cases in which the victim was subjected to blackmail involving intimate materials (e.g., nude photographs or videos) that the perpetrator had obtained through manipulation, impersonation, or technical interference. A defining feature of this category is the explicit threat of publishing such material unless the victim	I sent an intimate photo of me in my underwear to a guy from Germany and since then he has been constantly forcing me to send him more, but already nude photos, which I did because I was afraid he would post it somewhere. This has been going on for over a

	<p>complies-often involving financial demands, requests for additional explicit content, or other forms of coercion.</p>	<p>week now unfortunately and I really don't know what to do anymore because he has also sent social media to my classmates and he texts me that if I don't send more pictures he will send them. Which I've been uncomfortable with since it started, but I'm scared more and more and I just don't know what to do anymore.</p>
Sexting	<p>This category encompasses cases involving the voluntary or unintentional exchange of intimate materials or sexually explicit messages between users, which did not escalate into blackmail or coercion. The cases in this category reflect a range of digital interactions that, while often emotionally distressing or risky, did not involve explicit threats or demands.</p> <p>Four subtypes were identified within this category:</p> <p>Leakage of Intimate Content Cases in which intimate materials were unintentionally shared or forwarded without the consent of the original sender.</p> <p>Fear of Potential Misuse Situations in which individuals expressed concern that their intimate content might be misused, even though no actual blackmail or coercion had occurred.</p> <p>One-Sided Sexting Instances where the perpetrator sent unsolicited intimate messages or materials. In these cases, the affected individual sought advice or support in response to the unsolicited content.</p>	<p>Hi, there's a thing that happened that's entirely my fault. I'm 17 years old, and I sent naked pictures of myself to someone. I was supposed to pay for them, but they blocked me. I didn't take a picture of my head on purpose. What am I supposed to do? Is there any way to deal with this? Can something happen?</p>
Cyberbullying	<p>Repeated and deliberate harming through digital means (social networks, messages, forums) that has psychologically serious consequences for the victim. In addition to frequency and duration, perceived distress and intensity of impact were also clues that distinguished cases from one-off or less severe hate speech.</p>	<p>My friends and I are dealing with cyberbullying and death threats. We had a group where we wrote down who was doing what, etc. However, unfortunately 3 people have gotten on there who are showing racism, xenophobia, aggression, death threats and taunting because of their appearance. They send our photos when the mocking takes place. What can I do to stop this from happening further?</p>
Account breach	<p>Unauthorised access to a personal digital account (e.g. social networking, email) by obtaining a password or breaching security. Cases typically involved loss of control of the account and risk of misuse.</p>	<p>Hello my problem is that, my ex who I am not with for approx over 2 years is constantly hacking into my social networks (instagram,facebook), I change my password constantly and it doesn't work, and I am sure it is my ex</p>

		boyfriend sitting type phone and site. I would like advice on how to handle this further , should I go to the police with this? Thank you in advance.
Hating	Hateful, abusive or derogatory comments or messages directed at the victim, but which do not exhibit the systematic, repetitive or psychologically devastating impact typical of cyberbullying.	My ex-boyfriend's best friend texted me out of the blue with the abbreviation kys(kill yourself) and then texted more insults and deleted one voicemail (it said I'm a whore that no one cares about and I should kill myself) and I don't know what to do about it, whether to just block him or take it further
Digital footprint	Cases where a user has voluntarily published personal or intimate content (e.g. video, photographs) whose subsequent existence on the internet is perceived as undesirable or harmful. Typically, there is helplessness in attempting to remove this content.	Hello I need advice on how to deal with this problem.My daughter, 17, had her photos stolen, apparently copied from Instagram to another account under her name where there is a link to a sexually themed site. Instagram reported it but what about the site that created a profile for my daughter and offers videos for money?I am attaching a profile that is not my daughter's.
Fraud	A variety of fraudulent practices to enrich themselves at the expense of the victim - e.g. fake travel offers, fraudulent e-shops or identities. A common feature is the financial motivation of the perpetrator.	Hello, today a lady I know from old school messaged me on instagram chat to give her my number. when I asked why she wanted it, she said it was for a contest, so I sent it to her. then i got 2 messages from vodafone with the code and i had to send her a screenshot. I did it before I read the messages. They said they'd charge me over 1000 kc of my credit. i don't know what to do now, i think some hacker wrote from her account and now he has access to my money. I need help
Cybergrooming	Contacting a minor to build trust, manipulate and possibly persuade them to meet in person or exchange intimate content. Typical characteristics are prolonged and gradual escalation of intimacy.	A man I know, who is about 60 years old, sends me messages saying he would like to strip, invite me for coffee, take pictures of me in various women's clothes, and just text me when I get there so he can hug and caress me. And he implies that he would like me to do that and so on.
Phishing	Attempts to obtain sensitive data (e.g. login credentials, credit card numbers) through fraudulent emails or messages posing as legitimate communications from a trusted institution.	I have been a victim of phishing. I think it started with me opening an email in spam, I didn't click on any link and didn't download anything, I just opened it. He got a trojan into my PC and according to him had access to my camera, microphone etc for a few weeks. He said he has records of me, my photo and more.

	<p>He ended it all by submitting one of my passwords. At the same time he blackmails me by sending videos of me pleasuring myself to my friends, family and others. He says he'll delete everything if I send him \$500 to an anonymous cryptocurrency account.</p>
<p>Romance scam Impersonation of another person (often attractive or military) in the context of establishing a romantic relationship to obtain money or intimate material. Perpetrators often appear trustworthy and use emotional manipulation.</p>	<p>Hello, I have a problem with a "boyfriend". He is posing as a Czech who has moved to the US, is a model for Calvin Klein, Versace and is now in training in Gorgie as a soldier (last training there was 64 years ago). I have been corresponding with him for over 2 months, we call each other (voice, not on camera). I have contacted his ex-girlfriend, Marketa. She told me that they never saw each other, just called each other. She told me she thinks she's my classmate. The guy's name is Patrick. She said Natalie has the same expression as Patrik, a pretty similar voice (Patrik sounds 14-15, she said he's 19) and the same laugh. I didn't believe it at first but alas, I have plenty of evidence that it's my classmate Natalie. A friend of a friend sent Patrick a page that let him know via IP address where Patrick is, give or take. Nothing out of state showed up, so even that's a little evidence that she's a classmate. My friends and I wanted to go to the police because it's not fun anymore-a classmate didn't confess. She says it's not her. You're the last chance to help me and my friends. Please get in touch as soon as possible, we need to find out if my classmate is or not.</p>
<p>Sexual exploitation More serious cases of commercially motivated sexual abuse, e.g. the creation and distribution of intimate content with minors, including cases where the material is obtained within the family.</p>	<p>My brother has taken nude photos and videos of me, without my knowledge and then sent it on to various people either for money or for nude photos in return, I am underage and have even texted a guy saying he will send it on if they don't meet then immediately deleted the conversation. I reported my brother to the police, but they said they couldn't do anything about it as I had no</p>

		evidence and now I have no idea what to do
Photo manipulation	Manipulation of photography Abuse of image material to create photomontages, often with intimate content. This category includes so-called deepfakes, which are used to ridicule, intimidate or blackmail the victim.	An account took a picture of my face,put someone's penis under the picture,and is threatening to send it to my family and friends if I don't pay them,the account wrote that it was someone other than the profile picture.I don't know what to do
Threats	Threats and blackmail outside sextortion	At school during recess I started getting strange phone calls and after the experience I started answering strange numbers. A boy's voice answered and started threatening me in various ways, even making disgusting references to my mom. I don't know who it could be, but I'm scared. I am attaching a screen of the already blocked phone number that someone called me from.
Others	Cases that do not fall into any category	Hello, I have already written to the helpline about this problem. She referred me here. I recently came across a site containing child pornography on the social networking site Discord. I did so out of curiosity, not knowing what I would see. I don't know if it was really child pornography, but in any case I wanted to report the server and I downloaded a video as evidence. But before I could report the server, my account was blocked by Discord. I deleted the video immediately. But now I'm afraid I'll get caught by the police for possessing child pornography. I really only had it downloaded for a few minutes. I don't know what to do. If the police find out, my whole world will come crashing down. Thank you for your answer.

3. Results

The final research sample consisted of 901 respondents aged 10 to 17 years. Gender identification was available for 862 participants (95.7% of the total sample), with 39 respondents (4.3%) remaining unidentified. Among those with an identified gender, respondents identifying as a girl represented the clear majority with 571 participants (63.4% of identified cases), while those identifying as a boy accounted for 291 participants (32.3% of identified cases). The age distribution ranged from 10 to 17 years. The largest age group was 15-year-olds, representing 20.4% of respondents (n = 184), followed by 14-year-olds at 18.5% (n = 167). There were also significant numbers of 13-year-olds (n = 151, 16.8%) and 16-year-olds (n = 152, 16.9%). Early adolescents between the ages of 10 and 12 years collectively made up 14.3% of the sample, with 10-year-olds at 2.4% (n = 22), 11-year-olds at 4.6% (n = 41), and 12-year-olds at 7.3% (n = 66). The oldest group, 17-year-olds, comprised 13.1% (n = 118) of the sample. This distribution highlights a bell-shaped pattern with peak representation during middle adolescence, notably between the ages of 13 and 16.

Figure 2

Distribution of cases by age and gender

N = 901

The higher number of cases in which girls sought assistance is also reflected in the table below (Figure 3), which categorizes individual incidents according to types of risky online communication. In the vast majority of cases—except for those related to fraud—girls were more likely to reach out to the helpline. The figure also summarizes the most prevalent phenomena that children reported to the helpline, including sextortion, sexting, cyberbullying, online hate, and account breaches.

Figure 3

Frequency of individual categories of risky online communication

Type	Total Cases	Boys	Boys (%)	Girls	Girls (%)
Sextortion	283	98	34,6	180	63,6
Sexting	133	27	20,3	103	77,4
Cyberbullying	111	43	38,7	63	56,8
Other	91	26	28,6	55	60,4
Hating	62	12	19,4	45	72,6
Phishing & Fraud	62	32	51,6	24	38,7
Account Hacking	60	26	43,3	31	51,7
Digital Footprint	50	16	32	32	64
Cybergrooming	27	5	18,5	22	81,5
Threats	10	4	40	6	60
Romance Scam	7	0	0	7	100
Sexual Exploitation	5	2	40	3	60

We were also interested in whether there are statistically significant differences in the various types of risky virtual communication based on gender. Given the gender imbalance in the research sample, we conducted Fisher's exact test to determine the differences between the observed and expected frequencies by gender.

Figure 4

Expected versus observed cases by gender

We investigated gender disparities in five principal categories of risky online behaviour—namely sextortion, sexting, cyberbullying, hating, and phishing/fraud—by employing

Fisher's exact test to assess whether the distribution of boys and girls within each category deviates significantly from the overall gender composition of the sample (approximately 34% boys and 66% girls).

The analysis yielded three distinct patterns. First, girls were found to be significantly overrepresented in cases of sexting (27 boys vs. 103 girls, $p = 0.0004$) and hating (12 boys vs. 45 girls, $p = 0.039$). Second, boys were significantly overrepresented in phishing and fraud-related behaviors (32 boys vs. 24 girls, $p = 0.00018$). Third, no statistically significant gender-based differences were observed in the incidence of sextortion (98 boys vs. 180 girls, $p \approx 0.50$) or cyberbullying (43 boys vs. 63 girls, $p \approx 0.12$), indicating that the distribution in these categories aligns closely with the overall gender ratio.

Figure 5
Frequency of cases types

Beyond gender-based differences, we also examined how the prevalence of digital risk phenomena evolved over time. The annual data demonstrate a marked upward trend in digital risk phenomena over the study period (2013-2024). In the initial year, 2013, overall incidents were modest, with early reports in key categories setting a baseline that reflects a relatively low level of digital risk exposure among minors.

By 2020, however, a significant escalation is evident. For example, sexting was reported in 22 cases, while cyberbullying, hating, and sextortion were recorded at 6, 8, and 18 cases respectively, with account breach at 4 cases. This early surge indicates emerging vulnerabilities as digital interactions intensified over time. In 2021, further increases were observed. sexting, while fluctuating slightly to 19 cases, was accompanied by noticeable rises in cyberbullying (11 cases) and sextortion (24 cases), with account breach incidents more than doubling to 9 cases. The upward trajectory continued into 2022 when sextortion peaked at 47 cases - the

highest among the incidents - while sexting reported 14 cases, and account breach climbed to 12 cases, although Cyberbullying and Hating decreased to 4 and 6 cases respectively. These shifts highlight a differential growth in digital risk phenomena, with some categories (in this case sextortion) intensifying at a more rapid pace than others. By 2023, the trends reflect a stabilization in some areas while sextortion further escalated to 57 cases; cyberbullying, meanwhile, increased to 15 cases, indicative of a continued evolution in digital risk scenarios among minors. While sexting declined slightly to 11 cases and hating remained constant at 6 cases, the overall data from these key years unequivocally underscore a sustained increase in particular areas of risk. All trends are visually summarized in Figure 5.

Figure 6

Distribution of digital risks by age

The age-based analysis reveals clear developmental patterns in the prevalence of digital risk phenomena among children and adolescents aged 10 to 17. The data show that these risks are highly age-dependent, with the most pronounced peaks occurring during early to mid-adolescence.

Sexting stands out as one of the most prevalent digital risks. Among the youngest children (ages 10-11), sexting cases are minimal, with only 1 to 5 cases reported. However, there is a sharp increase starting at age 12 (11 cases), which accelerates through age 13 (24 cases) and peaks at age 14 (32 cases). While the numbers dip slightly at age 15 (21 cases) and 17 (14 cases), the overall trend highlights a much higher vulnerability to sexting among adolescents compared to younger children.

Cyberbullying follows a somewhat different trajectory. It is already present at age 10 (7 cases) and rises steadily, reaching 14 cases by age 13. The peak occurs at age 15, with 31

cases, before the numbers decrease in the later teen years. This pattern suggests that early to mid-adolescence is a particularly sensitive period for cyberbullying risk. Sextortion, while less frequent than sexting or cyberbullying, shows a concerning escalation with age. There are no cases at age 10, but the numbers jump to 5 at age 11, 13 at age 12, and then surge to 41 at age 13. The highest risk is observed at age 15, with 77 cases, and the numbers remain elevated through ages 16 (53 cases) and 17 (48 cases). This trend underscores the increasing vulnerability to exploitative behaviors as adolescents grow older.

Phishing & Fraud incidents are relatively rare across all ages, but there is a modest peak at age 15 (10 cases), indicating that account-related risks also become more relevant in mid-adolescence. Hating, on the other hand, is most frequent at age 13 (19 cases) and remains notable at ages 12 (7 cases), 14 (5 cases), and 16 (10 cases), suggesting that negative online interactions are particularly common during these years. In summary, the data make it clear that the developmental window between ages 13 and 15 is especially critical. During this period, both sexting and cyberbullying reach their highest levels, and sextortion cases escalate dramatically. These findings highlight the need for targeted prevention and intervention efforts focused on early to mid-adolescence, when engagement with digital platforms and susceptibility to digital risks are at their peak.

Figure 7

Platform usage trends over years

An analysis of the platforms used by children during incidents of risky virtual communication reveals several noteworthy trends and distinct numerical patterns. Facebook was the dominant platform in the early years, starting with 10 recorded cases in 2013 and peaking at 26 cases in both 2016 and 2017. However, its prominence declined sharply in subsequent years, dropping to just 2 cases by 2024—an over 90% decrease from its peak. In contrast, Instagram demonstrated a pronounced and sustained increase in reported usage. While it was virtually absent in the earliest years, Instagram cases began to rise steadily, reaching 9 cases in 2018, 16 in 2019, and peaking at 29 cases in 2022. This high level of usage persisted, with 28 cases recorded in both 2023 and 2024. This represents a net increase of 28 cases over the observation period, marking a substantial shift in platform preference among youth.

Snapchat exhibited the most consistent upward trajectory of all platforms. It was not mentioned at all in the early years, but by 2018 it appeared in the data, and its frequency grew steadily, reaching 14 cases in 2024—the highest for this platform and a clear sign of its growing relevance in recent years.

Discord, a platform that entered the dataset later, showed a gradual but steady rise. It first appeared in 2021 with 6 cases, and while its numbers are lower than those of Instagram or Snapchat, it maintained a presence with 5 cases in 2024, indicating its growing adoption among adolescents.

TikTok, which was absent in the early years, experienced rapid adoption beginning around 2019. Its frequency increased quickly, reaching its highest recorded value of 6 cases in 2024. This late but sharp rise highlights the platform's recent surge in popularity and its growing role in the digital lives of young people.

4. Discussion

The findings of this research clearly indicate statistically significant differences between boys and girls in terms of how frequently they seek help in relation to risky online behaviours. Girls constituted a substantially larger portion of the research sample and were predominant in most of the observed categories. However, statistical testing accounted for this imbalance (Fisher's exact test) was used to evaluate the relationship between gender and specific types of help-seeking behavior, controlling for the unequal group sizes.

The discrepancies between expected and observed frequencies were particularly striking in the cases of sexting and online hate, with p-values indicating that these differences are unlikely to have occurred by chance alone. This suggests, on the one hand, a greater exposure or vulnerability of girls in certain types of online interactions, and on the other- perhaps more notably- a higher propensity to seek help when faced with sexting and sextortion. This finding that girls might share their problems more likely than boys aligns with the results of the EU Kids Online research (Smahel et al., 2020), which indicates that in most countries, girls and younger children are more likely than boys and older children to communicate with their parents about their online activities.

For example, (Dolev-Cohen & Ricon, 2020) found that boys are more likely to initiate requests for intimate images. However, the overall level of engagement in sexting does not differ significantly between genders. In our study, statistical significance in the sexting category may have been achieved because we included cases in which children sought help after being proposed sexting, or when another person had already sent them intimate materials. Given that boys more frequently initiate sexting, girls may be more often subjected to pressure to engage in such behavior, which may explain their higher representation in this category. However, this remains a hypothesis that requires further empirical investigation.

Research findings regarding whether boys or girls are more often victims of cyberbullying and other forms of cyberaggression are mixed. Some studies have found that boys are more frequently targeted (Lee et al., 2018) while others suggest that gender does not play a significant role (Hinduja & Patchin, 2009) Marinoni et al. (2023) provide an explanation as to why girls might be more vulnerable to certain types of online aggression and why more girls report incidents of online hate. One possible explanation is that boys tend to engage more frequently in physical forms of bullying (Dehue et al., 2008) whereas girls are more likely to be involved in verbal aggression (Slonje et al., 2013) This difference in bullying modalities may partially account for the observed gender differences in reporting behaviors related to online hate.

Age plays a crucial role in risky virtual communication, as reflected in our data, mostly in sexting and sextortion. **The most vulnerable group in both sexting and sextortion incidents comprises adolescents aged 14 to 16.** For example, Parti et al. (2022) found that significantly more middle school students than high school students perceived

sexting as safer than sexual intercourse, and were more likely to disagree with the notion that one should be emotionally connected to the person they sext with.

These attitudes suggest that sexting can be perceived as normative in early adolescence, functioning as a form of social interaction or experimentation, rather than an expression of sexual desire. As such, sexting may occur at the age of 15 or even earlier, without being directly associated. Finally, a meta analysis from Madigan et al. (2018b) has demonstrated that the prevalence of sexting tends to increase with participants' age - being notably higher among sexually active adolescents compared to their sexually inactive peers. Additionally, sexting rates have shown a rising trend over time across different cohorts, and vary by modality, with higher prevalence observed when mobile devices are used compared to computers. As a result, the increasing accessibility of smartphones at younger ages is likely contributing to an earlier onset of sexting behaviour among adolescents.

As we can see from the results of our analysis, the number of cases of risky virtual behaviour (mainly sextortion) has been increasing and has seen a rapid increase especially since 2019. Sextortion is experienced by both girls and boys, it occurs both in the context of establishing new online contacts and existing relationships, as well as, for example, after a breakup (blackmailing ex-partners). A separate category is sextortion, which is associated with a person whose identity the child does not know and does not have their identity verified and who demands, for example, money or other intimate materials.

When communicating with unknown users, children are able to communicate in different languages - both their mother tongue (Czech) and English, for example, so the language and geographical barrier falls here. However, this also applies to the person with whom the child communicates - in many cases it is not possible to determine which country they really come from - they can also use intelligent tools that allow them to translate, for example, in a large number of languages.

The results also show how their preferences in the use of social networks and other communication tools where risky behaviour occurs are changing - most often children report incidents related to Instagram, followed by Snapchat, TikTok and Discord.

5. Recommendation

A. Recommendations for parents

Parents **should start talking to their children about the safe use of digital technologies at an early age**, ideally when the child starts working with a mobile phone, tablet or computer. Factual, age-appropriate communication is appropriate that clearly explains the basic rules of online safety to children without unnecessarily intimidating them. From the beginning, the child should be sure that **they can confide in their parents about any problem that happens to them in the digital environment** and that they will not be punished or criticized for it.

The **technical security of the devices** used by children plays a crucial role. Parents should set parental controls, enable appropriate restrictions (e.g., content filtering), and regularly check installed apps. In the case of younger children, it is also desirable to limit the use of digital technologies in time, not only to prevent risky behaviour, but also to protect the child's mental and physical health.

Trust, consistency and openness on the part of parents are the key to a child being willing to share any negative experiences and seeking help in time.

B. Recommendations for teachers and other educators

Educators and other professionals in the field of education should **integrate the topic of online safety into the classroom systematically and over the long term**, not see it as an isolated one-off activity. Prevention should be conducted in a positive way - the aim is not to scare children, but to provide them with the skills, information and confidence they need to move safely in the digital world.

It is essential to work with specific and real examples that will bring the issue closer to children in a comprehensible form. Case studies, anonymised stories or simulations of crisis situations are suitable means of developing critical thinking and decision-making skills. Children should actively participate in discussions, look for solutions and learn how to react in risky situations.

Preventive work in schools should also include **providing practical instructions, such as how to report objectionable content, how to block contact or where to turn in case of a problem**. Teachers should also be prepared to recognise warning signs in pupils and, if necessary, cooperate with the school counselling centre or other professional institutions.

C. Recommendations for children

Children and adolescents should be led to realize that even in the online environment, **there are rules that protect their safety and privacy**. They should know that no one has the right to force them to send intimate material, reveal personal information, or engage in inappropriate activities. If they find themselves in a situation that makes them uncomfortable, they should know that they have the right to say "no", block the contact and confide in a trusted adult.

It is essential that **children know the basic rules of digital safety** - setting privacy on social networks, using strong passwords, recognising fraudulent messages and risky behaviour from others. They should be led to the fact that sharing any content has its consequences and that it is always appropriate to consider whether they would be comfortable if someone else saw the shared material.

Empathy and solidarity should also be part of prevention - children should know that if their peer is facing online harassment, they can support them and encourage them to seek help. Open communication, the ability to recognize the risk and the awareness that they are not alone in the problem are key factors in effective protection.

6. Acknowledgement

This output/article has been produced with the support of the project ReDiKid: Resilient Child in the Digital World, reg. no. CZ.02.01.01/00/23_025/0008686 co-funded by the EU.

7. References

- Abubakari, Y. (2024). Modelling the modus operandi of online romance fraud: Perspectives of online romance fraudsters. *Journal of Economic Criminology*, 6, 100112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JECONC.2024.100112>
- Almeida, T. C., & Pereira, A. (2025). Prevalence of grooming and sexting among Portuguese youth: Adaptation of the Questionnaire for Online Sexual Solicitation and Interactions with Adults and Sexting Questionnaire. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 171, 108179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHILDYOUTH.2025.108179>
- Amadori, A., & Brighi, A. (2025). Technology-facilitated sexual violence among sexual and gender minority youth: The moderating role of digital resilience. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 166, 108576. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHB.2025.108576>
- Anastassiou, A. (2017). Sexting and Young People: A Review of the Qualitative Literature. *The Qualitative Report*, 22(8), 2231–2239. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2017.2951>
- Anderson, M., & Jiang, J. (2018). Research Associate Aaron Smith, Associate Director Tom Caiazza, Communications Manager 202.419.4372 www.pewresearch.org RECOMMENDED CITATION Pew Research Center. *Teens, Social Media & Technology*. www.pewresearch.org.
- Brighi, A., Amadori, A., Summerer, K., & Menin, D. (2023). Prevalence and risk factors for nonconsensual distribution of intimate images among Italian young adults: Implications for prevention and intervention. *International Journal of Clinical and Health Psychology*, 23(4), 100414. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJCHP.2023.100414>
- Centrum PRVoK. (2025). <https://www.prvok.upol.cz/>
- Cerolini, S., Vacca, M., Zegretti, A., Zagaria, A., & Lombardo, C. (2024). Body shaming and internalized weight bias as potential precursors of eating disorders in adolescents. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15, 1356647. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FPSYG.2024.1356647/BIBTEX>

- Chen, H., He, M., & Peng, L. (2025). Understanding online shopping fraud among Chinese elderly: Extending routine activity theory in the online context. *Telematics and Informatics*, 96, 102208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TELE.2024.102208>
- Cross, C., Holt, K., & Holt, T. J. (2023). To pay or not to pay: An exploratory analysis of sextortion in the context of romance fraud. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17488958221149581>.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/17488958221149581>
- Cross, C., Holt, K., & O'Malley, R. L. (2023). "If U Don't Pay they will Share the Pics": Exploring Sextortion in the Context of Romance Fraud. *Victims & Offenders*, 18(7), 1194–1215. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15564886.2022.2075064>
- Dehue, F., Bolman, C., & Völlink, T. (2008). Cyberbullying: Youngsters' experiences and parental perception. *Cyberpsychology and Behavior*, 11(2), 217–223. <https://doi.org/10.1089/CPB.2007.0008;CTYPE:STRING:JOURNAL>
- Dobešová, P., Sztokowski, R., & Kopecký, K. (2023). Sexting u žáků na 1. stupni základní školy. *Sexting u Žáků Na 1. Stupni Základní Školy*. <https://doi.org/10.5507/PDF.23.24463759>
- Dolev-Cohen, M., & Ricon, T. (2020). Demystifying sexting: Adolescent sexting and its associations with parenting styles and sense of parental social control in Israel. *Cyberpsychology: Journal of Psychosocial Research on Cyberspace*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.5817/CP2020-1-6>
- Döring, N. (2014). Consensual sexting among adolescents: Risk prevention through abstinence education or safer sexting? *Cyberpsychology: Journal of Psychosocial Research on Cyberspace*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.5817/CP2014-1-9>
- Gala, J., & Kapadia, S. (2013). Romantic Relationships in Emerging Adulthood: A Developmental Perspective. *Psychological Studies* 2013 58:4, 58(4), 406–418. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12646-013-0219-5>
- Gámez-Guadix, M., De Santisteban, P., Wachs, S., & Wright, M. (2021). Unraveling cyber sexual abuse of minors: Psychometrics properties of the Multidimensional Online Grooming Questionnaire and prevalence by sex and age. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 120, 105250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHIABU.2021.105250>
- Gámez-Guadix, M., Mateos-Pérez, E., Wachs, S., Wright, M., Martínez, J., & Íncera, D. (2022). Assessing image-based sexual abuse: Measurement, prevalence, and temporal stability of sextortion and nonconsensual sexting ("revenge porn") among adolescents. *Journal of Adolescence*, 94(5), 789–799. <https://doi.org/10.1002/JAD.12064>
- Hasse, A., Cortesi, S., Lombana-Bermudez, A., & Gasser, U. (2019). *Youth and Cyberbullying: Another Look*. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3477297>
- Henry, N., Flynn, A., & Powell, A. (2019). *Responding to "revenge pornography": Prevalence, nature and impacts*.
- Henry, N., & Umbach, R. (2024). Sextortion: Prevalence and correlates in 10 countries. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 158, 108298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHB.2024.108298>
- Hinduja, S., & Patchin, J. W. (2009). Bullying beyond the schoolyard. *Preventing and Responding to Cyberbullying*.
- Hinduja, S., & Patchin, J. W. (2021). *Cyberbullying Data 2019 - Cyberbullying Research Center*. <https://cyberbullying.org/2019-cyberbullying-data>

- Hinduja, S., & Patchin, J. W. (2024). *2023 Cyberbullying Data - Cyberbullying Research Center*. <https://cyberbullying.org/2023-cyberbullying-data>
- Hollá, K. (2013). *Kyberšikana*. <https://www.martinus.cz/609843-kybersikana/kniha>
- Kabali, H. K., Irigoyen, M. M., Nunez-Davis, R., Budacki, J. G., Mohanty, S. H., Leister, K. P., & Bonner, R. L. (2015). Exposure and Use of Mobile Media Devices by Young Children. *Pediatrics*, *136*(6), 1044–1050. <https://doi.org/10.1542/PEDS.2015-2151>
- Kopecký, K. (2016). *Kyberšikana a její specifika v prostředí systému primární prevence rizikového chování (habilitační práce)*.
- Kopecký, K. (2017). Online blackmail of Czech children focused on so-called “sextortion” (analysis of culprit and victim behaviors). *Telematics and Informatics*, *34*(1), 11–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TELE.2016.04.004>
- Kopecký, K., & Szotkowski, R. (2017). *Kyberšikana a další formy kybernetické agrese. Metodické doporučení k primární prevenci rizikového chování u dětí a mládeže MŠMT (21291/2010-28)*. https://view.officeapps.live.com/op/view.aspx?src=https%3A%2F%2Fmsmt.gov.cz%2Fuploads%2FPriloha_c._7_Kybersikana_d.docx&wdOrigin=BROWSELINK
- Kraag, G., Schmidt, J., & Münster, F. H. (2021). Body Shaming: an Exploratory Study on its Definition and Classification. *Article in International Journal of Bullying Prevention*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42380-021-00109-3>
- Kristiansen, S., Jensen, A. V., Nimgaard, M., & Ludvigsen, E. (2024). Virtual item trade scams: A typology of young victims. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02697580241258786>
- Kumar, V. L., & Goldstein, M. A. (2020). Cyberbullying and Adolescents. *Current Pediatrics Reports*, *8*(3), 86–92. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S40124-020-00217-6/TABLES/2>
- Leduc, K., Nagar, P. M., Caivano, O., & Talwar, V. (2022). “The thing is, it follows you everywhere”: Child and adolescent conceptions of cyberbullying. *Computers in Human Behavior*, *130*, 107180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHB.2022.107180>
- Lee, J. M., Hong, J. S., Yoon, J., Peguero, A. A., & Seok, H. J. (2018). Correlates of Adolescent Cyberbullying in South Korea in Multiple Contexts: A Review of the Literature and Implications for Research and School Practice. *Deviant Behavior*, *39*(3), 293–308. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01639625.2016.1269568;PAGE:STRING:ARTICLE/CHAPTER>
- Lippman, J. R., & Campbell, S. W. (2014). Damned If You Do, Damned If You Don’t...If You’re a Girl: Relational and Normative Contexts of Adolescent Sexting in the United States. *Journal of Children and Media*, *8*(4), 371–386. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17482798.2014.923009>
- López-Vizcaíno, M. F., Nóvoa, F. J., Carneiro, V., & Casheda, F. (2021). Early detection of cyberbullying on social media networks. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, *118*, 219–229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FUTURE.2021.01.006>
- Madigan, S., Ly, A., Rash, C. L., Van Ouytsel, J., & Temple, J. R. (2018a). Prevalence of Multiple Forms of Sexting Behavior Among Youth: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *JAMA Pediatrics*, *172*(4), 327–335. <https://doi.org/10.1001/JAMAPEDIATRICS.2017.5314>
- Madigan, S., Ly, A., Rash, C. L., Van Ouytsel, J., & Temple, J. R. (2018b). Prevalence of multiple forms of sexting behavior among youth: A systematic review and meta-

- analysis. *JAMA Pediatrics*, 172(4), 327–335.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/JAMAPEDIATRICS.2017.5314>,
- Molla-Esparza, C., López-González, E., & Losilla, J. M. (2021). Sexting Prevalence and Socio-Demographic Correlates in Spanish Secondary School Students. *Sexuality Research and Social Policy*, 18(1), 97–111. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S13178-020-00434-0/METRICS>
- Moreno, M. A., & Radesky, J. (2023). Putting Forward a New Narrative for Adolescent Media: The American Academy of Pediatrics Center of Excellence on Social Media and Youth Mental Health. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 73(2), 227–229.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JADOHEALTH.2023.04.027>
- Mori, C., Cooke, J. E., Temple, J. R., Ly, A., Lu, Y., Anderson, N., Rash, C., & Madigan, S. (2020). The Prevalence of Sexting Behaviors Among Emerging Adults: A Meta-Analysis. *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, 49(4), 1103–1119.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/S10508-020-01656-4/METRICS>
- Mori, C., Park, J., Temple, J. R., & Madigan, S. (2022). Are Youth Sexting Rates Still on the Rise? A Meta-analytic Update. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 70(4), 531–539.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2021.10.026>
- Ojeda, M., Romera, E. M., & Del Rey, R. (2024). Nonconsensual Sexting: Are the Moral Processes the Same If Boys or Girls Appear in the Forwarded Content? *Https://Home.Liebertpub.Com/Cyber*, 27(2), 111–118.
<https://doi.org/10.1089/CYBER.2023.0412>
- Öztürk, F. Ö., Tamaddon, M., & Tezel, A. (2025). Cyberbullying, psychosocial problems and affecting factors among adolescents. *Archives of Psychiatric Nursing*, 54, 12–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APNU.2024.12.001>
- Parti, K., Sanders, C. E., & Englander, E. K. (2022). Sexting at an Early Age: Patterns and Poor Health-Related Consequences of Pressured Sexting in Middle and High School. *The Journal of School Health*, 93(1), 73.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/JOSH.13258>
- Patchin, J. W., & Hinduja, S. (2022). *Teen Sexting: A Brief Guide for Parents and Educators*. 1–10.
- Patchin, J. W., & Hinduja, S. (2024). The nature and extent of youth sextortion: Legal implications and directions for future research. *Behavioral Sciences & the Law*, 42(4), 401–416. <https://doi.org/10.1002/BSL.2667>
- Pérez-Rodríguez, P., Machimbarrena, J. M., Ortega-Barón, J., Díaz-López, A., Caba-Machado, V., & González-Cabrera, J. (2024). Peer cybervictimization and cyberaggression as a function of developmental stage during adolescence: A preliminary study. *Acta Psychologica*, 246, 104280.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ACTPSY.2024.104280>
- Pretorius, C., Chambers, D., Cowan, B., & Coyle, D. (2019). Young People Seeking Help Online for Mental Health: Cross-Sectional Survey Study. *JMIR Mental Health*, 6(8), e13524. <https://doi.org/10.2196/13524>
- Quesada, S., Fernández-González, L., & Calvete, E. (2018). EL SEXTEO (SEXTING) EN LA ADOLESCENCIA: FRECUENCIA Y ASOCIACIÓN CON LA VICTIMIZACIÓN DE CIBERACOSO Y VIOLENCIA EN EL NOVIAZGO 1. *Behavioral Psychology / Psicología Conductual*, 26, 225–242.
- Ray, A., & Henry, N. (2024). Sextortion: A Scoping Review. *Trauma, Violence & Abuse*, 26(1), 138. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15248380241277271>

- Renfrow, D. G., & Rollo, E. A. (2014). Sexting on Campus: Minimizing Perceived Risks and Neutralizing Behaviors. *Deviant Behavior, 35*(11), 903–920.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01639625.2014.897122>
- Ringrose, J., Gill, R., Livingstone, S., & Harvey, L. (2012). *A qualitative study of children, young people and “sexting”: a report prepared for the NSPCC*.
<http://www.nspcc.org.uk/>
- Santre, S. (2023). Cyberbullying in adolescents: A literature review. *International Journal of Adolescent Medicine and Health, 35*(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1515/IJAMH-2021-0133/PDF>
- Schlüter, C., Kraag, G., & Schmidt, J. (2023). Body Shaming: an Exploratory Study on its Definition and Classification. *International Journal of Bullying Prevention, 5*(1), 26–37. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S42380-021-00109-3>
- Slonje, R., Smith, P. K., & Frisén, A. (2013). The nature of cyberbullying, and strategies for prevention. *Computers in Human Behavior, 29*(1), 26–32.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHB.2012.05.024>
- Smahel, D., MacHackova, H., Mascheroni, G., Dedkova, L., Staksrud, E., Olafsson, K., Livingstone, S., & Hasebrink, U. (2020). *EU Kids Online 2020: survey results from 19 countries*. <https://doi.org/10.21953/LSE.47FDEQJ01OFO>
- Szotkowski, R., Kopecký, K., & Dobešová, P. (2020). Sexting u českých dětí. *Sexting u Českých Děťí*. <https://doi.org/10.5507/PDF.20.24457932>
- Wachs, S., Wright, M. F., Gámez-Guadix, M., Döring, N., Rey, R. Del, Michel, W., & Ojeda, M. (2021). How Are Consensual, Non-Consensual, and Pressured Sexting Linked to Depression and Self-Harm? The Moderating Effects of Demographic Variables. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 18*(5), 2597.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/IJERPH18052597>
- Walker, K., & Sleath, E. (2017). A systematic review of the current knowledge regarding revenge pornography and non-consensual sharing of sexually explicit media. *Aggression and Violent Behavior, 36*, 9–24.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.AVB.2017.06.010>
- Walsh, W. A., & Tener, D. (2022). “If you don’t send me five other pictures I am going to post the photo online”: A qualitative analysis of experiences of survivors of sextortion. *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse, 31*(4), 447–465.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10538712.2022.2067093>
- Wang, D., Duan, Y., & Jin, Y. (2025). Navigating online perils: Socioeconomic status, online activity lifestyles, and online fraud targeting and victimization of old adults in China. *Computers in Human Behavior, 162*, 108458.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHB.2024.108458>
- Wang, J., Zhang, L., Xu, L., & Qian, X. (2024). The dynamic emotional experience of online fraud victims during the process of being defrauded: A text-based analysis. *Journal of Criminal Justice, 94*, 102231.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCRIMJUS.2024.102231>
- Wittes, B., Poplin, C., Jurecic, Q., & Spera, C. (2016). *Sextortion: Cybersecurity, teenagers, and remote sexual assault 1*. <https://www.brookings.edu/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/sextortion1-1.pdf>
- Zeng, Q., Lin, L., Jiang, R., Huang, W., & Lin, D. (2025). NNEnsLeG: A novel approach for e-commerce payment fraud detection using ensemble learning and neural

networks. *Information Processing & Management*, 62(1), 103916.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IPM.2024.103916>

Zhu, C., Huang, S., Evans, R., & Zhang, W. (2021). Cyberbullying Among Adolescents and Children: A Comprehensive Review of the Global Situation, Risk Factors, and Preventive Measures. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 9, 634909.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/FPUBH.2021.634909/BIBTEX>